

Leadership Styles Influencing Job Satisfaction of Bank Employees in Developed ...

Leadership Styles Influencing Job Satisfaction of Bank Employees in Developed and Less-developed Cities of Sindh

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Abstract

This study evaluated the effects of traditional leadership styles on job satisfaction of bank employees, and data were collected through closed-ended questionnaire, composed of 16 items using four point Likert scale. Sample consists of 120 employees of banks, 66 from Hyderabad city and 54 from Badin city. Descriptive Statistics, Chi Square and Simple Regression was applied for data analysis. Findings demonstrate the moderate positive effect of democratic leadership style and strong positive effect of laissez-faire leadership style on job satisfaction, while autocratic style affects insignificantly on job satisfaction of bank employees in developed area. Whereas, Laissez-faire leadership style has significant positive and democratic leadership style has insignificant but positive effect, whereas autocratic leadership style has insignificant and negative effects on job satisfaction in less-developed area. The highest satisfaction towards laissez-faire style is signaling that employees tend to be happy when they are free from strict eye of their boss.

Keywords: Democratic, Autocratic, Laissez-Faire, Job Satisfaction, Bank employees

1. Introduction

Man is born free and by nature they want to be free from any interference and dictations by others, especially when it comes to perform any task. Leadership is defined as the skill of influencing others' behavior towards goals' achievement. Success and growth of an organization is largely contributed by effective leadership style.

There are various theories given about leadership. Theories that emphasize on personality, intellectual, physical and social qualities to distinguish between leaders and nonleaders are called trait theories. Leadership can be predicted by traits, but they are more probably used to predict leaders' emergence rather their effectiveness. Theories that propose the particular behaviors tell apart leaders from nonleaders are called behavioral theories. Trait and behavioral theories help us understanding leadership, whereas contingency theories add very important aspect of environment in understanding leadership effectiveness studies.

Throughout human history, leadership has been one of the pillars of human societies. The changes made by individuals and groups are attributed to leaders under whom the

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developments took place. Because major actions have been undertaken under the guidance of leaders (Shafie, Baghersalimi, & Barghi, 2013).

Behavioral theories emerged as a result of the great criticism on trait theories, which argued leaders are born because they have some innate qualities, on the contrary behavioral theories assert leaders can be made; by learning and training infinite leaders can be produced and for doing so a keen analysis of the behavior of successful leaders will help in chalking out the model of effective leaders, and deploying effective leaders will assist in attaining organizational effectiveness..

The effectiveness of three classical styles of leadership were sought to determine, that are seen in traditional groups and organizations. Job satisfaction of bank employees of developed and less-developed areas is taken as dependent variable. The Iowa Studies of leadership analyzed the styles by an experiment in 1938. Lewin, with Lippitt, and White attempted to analyze how various styles of leadership could affect the satisfaction, frustration-aggression levels of the individuals. They suggested the three styles.

1.1 Autocratic Leadership

Authoritarian leadership is another name used for autocratic leadership. This style of leadership contains overall autonomy of a leader, decisions are made on the basis of leader's own choices and judgments and there is least or no participation of followers in decision making.

1.2 Democratic Leadership

Participative leadership is another name used for Democratic leadership, which embraces followers' participation in decision-making process along with full guidance and support of the leader.

1.3 Laissez-Faire Leadership

Delegating leadership is other name given to laissez-faire leadership. Another term used for laissez-faire is 'nonexistence of leader', as leaders are laid-back and do not intervene frequently, while followers are allowed for decision making. This is sometimes criticized as absence of leadership style.

1.4 Job Satisfaction

There are major job attitudes and job satisfaction is one of the immensely vital job attitudes that has been widely studied and it is also positively related to job performance. Robbins and Judge (2009) have explained job satisfaction in detail and termed it as the vital job attitude. Employees tend to analyze their job in terms of their inputs and outputs by the employer. Job satisfaction is favorable attitude of an individual towards his/her employment resulting from the assessment of what he/she gives and what he/she is given by employer. Thus, employer's role is immensely important in attaining job satisfaction of employees, and the satisfaction leads good performance of employee, and ultimately result in organizational development. To pursue a successful Banking system the job satisfaction of employees will help in better organizational performance that can be accomplished by effective leadership. This study sought to determine the effects of three leadership styles: Democratic, Autocratic and

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Laissez-faire on job satisfaction of employees in banks of developed and less-developed cities. Since various researchers have identified difference between the employees of rural and urban areas with regard to job satisfaction levels, and researchers have also recommended for identification of various factors as determinants for that difference. Therefore, this study will add a new insight into the literature about leadership styles, job satisfaction and bank employees of developed and less-developed areas. Hyderabad city was selected from developed areas, and Badin city was selected from less-developed cities.

2. Objectives of the Study

- To know about the style of leadership perceived to be applied in banks of developed and less-developed cities
- To determine the difference between bank employees' job satisfaction in developed and less-developed cities
- To know which leadership style affects more on bank employees' job satisfaction in developed and less-developed cities

3. Literature Review

The effectiveness of classic leadership styles was examined by Lewin, Lippitt and White (1939), they conducted an experiment on schoolchildren by assigning three styles of leaders to them. They found democratic leader as most effective as it was liked by nineteen out of twenty. Laissez-faire leader was preferred by seven out of ten boys to autocratic one, as they preferred confusion and chaos as compared to harshness and inflexibility present in the autocratic style. Most aggressive, hostile and uncaring behaviors of boys were witnessed under autocratic style and least under democratic style.

Teece, Pisano and Shuen (1997), and McGrath and MacMillan (2000) emphasized the identification of effective leadership style is immensely imperative for improvement of performance of organizations. Similarly, Mohammed, et al. (2014) concluded effective leaders also accord the worker's self-interest to the interest of employees or the group. If motivational factors are used by leaders, and job satisfaction of employees is considered in decision making process and promotion; the workers and the leaders will have efficient and effective coordination, as a result organization will get maximum benefits as a whole.

Omolayo (2007) conducted research on 200 workers of four manufacturing organizations in Nigeria and argued that there was higher civic sense and less frustration about their job as exhibited by workers under democratic leaders as compared to employees under autocratic leaders. Moreover, Schwartz (1987) pointed frustration and aggression is found in organizations under autocracy while high obedience was found among workers in democratic organizations. Likewise, Smith (1998) admired democratic style as it mostly results in highly enthusiastic team by involving all members of a group. Furthermore, Mgbodile (2004) opines that autocratic leadership style seems to be self-centered style and doesn't allow significant participation of the followers in affairs of organization as compared to democratic style which is employee-oriented and encourages the participation of the followers.

Bhatti *et al* (2012) established that job satisfaction is affected positively by leadership style through a research study conducted on sample of 205 teachers working at public and private

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schools in Lahore. They advocated democratic leadership style and stated that employees like the atmosphere where they can communicate easily with leader and express their views without any fear which will result in job satisfaction. Similarly, Shamaki (2015) opined that democratic principals affect more positively to their teachers' job satisfaction. He also found more competent teachers under democratic principals of public schools, in contrast with teachers under autocratic principals. In the same way, Nadarasa and Thuraisingam (2014) found positive influence of democratic principals on teachers' job satisfaction and negative influence of autocratic principals on teachers' job satisfaction, while studying that how principals of school lead and how their leading style affect teachers' job satisfaction with a sample of 90 teachers of secondary schools in Jaffna educational zone of Sri Lanka.

Smith and Peterson (1988) argued that least work interest and lack of morale are caused by absence of leadership style which is laissez-faire style while, good morale is maintained and level of work also remains steady in democratic leadership style, but autocratic style is most efficient if productivity is considered the main concern of a group. Besides, Chaudhry and Javed (2012) concluded that there was insignificant relation found between laissez-faire style of leadership and motivation of employees, and therefore should not be considered as an important leadership style. Shafie, et al. (2013) argued that anarchy and confusion are the results of laissez-faire leadership style in the organization, since everyone assumed to be a leader in the organization. Likewise, Skogstad *et al* (2007) regarded laissez-faire leadership style as a detrimental leadership style. While, Hinkin and Schriesheim (2008) labeled 'the nonexistence of leadership' for the laissez-faire leadership.

Khan, Asghar and Zaheer (2014) established that employee job satisfaction has higher influence of transformational leadership style, if it is compared with the influence of transactional style, while examining the influence of two alternate types of leadership styles on bank employees' job satisfaction in Islamabad region. They suggested to check more leadership styles' influence on job satisfaction of bank employees in future.

The literature urges to examine the classic leadership styles for determining their influence on job satisfaction of employees, since democratic leadership style is immensely advocated, whereas autocratic and laissez-faire styles are widely criticized in the literature.

Urban and rural employment have different job environments and employees' job attitudes. Fossum (1974) found in his experiment that rural participants have more satisfaction towards their job as compared to urban participants. Moreover, Arnold and Seekins (1997) have also described that there are differences in the job satisfaction level of urban and rural employees. Likewise, Gellis, Kim and Hwang (2004) established that job satisfaction level of urban and rural areas is really different, after surveying in New York. As the managers of urban areas found to have more problems with their job as compared to managers of rural areas. They also asserted that urban managers highlighted more issues of supervisory support, relationship with supervisor and quality of supervision, as compared to managers of rural areas. Besides, Emmerich (2003) argued that no significant difference has been found between the job satisfaction levels of urban and rural employees. Thus, it is imperative to analyze the influence of the classic leadership styles on bank employees' job satisfaction, who are working in developed and less-developed areas.

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4. Hypotheses & Conceptual Model

There has been three hypotheses developed in the study, and the conceptual model of the study is exhibit in Figure 1.

H1: Democratic leadership style has significant and positive influence, whereas autocratic and laissez-faire leadership styles have significant negative influences on Job Satisfaction of bank employees in developed cities

H2: Democratic leadership style has significant and positive influence, whereas autocratic and laissez-faire leadership styles have significant negative influences on Job Satisfaction of bank employees in less-developed cities

H3: There is a significant difference between influence of leadership styles on job satisfaction of bank employees in developed and bank employees in less-developed cities

Figure 1. Conceptual Model

5. Methodology

5.1. Sample

This is a quantitative study using convenient sampling for selectin of cities and simple random sampling technique for selection of respondents. Sample composed of 120 employees of banks located in two cities of Sindh; one developed city Hyderabad and second less-developed city Badin. Total 80 questionnaires were distributed in Hyderabad out of which 72 were received and 80 were also distributed in Badin out of which only 59 were received. Khan, Asghar and Zaheer (2014) took sample size of 124 bank employees of the Islamabad region in similar kind of study. Six questionnaires of Hyderabad and five of Badin were incomplete therefore were discarded and total 120 — 66 of Hyderabad and 54 of Badin — were analyzed.

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5.2. Instrument

Data for the study were collected through self-administered, closed-ended questionnaire, composed of 16 items using four point Likert scale i.e. 1= strongly disagree to 4 = strongly agree. Four items were measuring their job satisfaction, out of which two were adopted from Spector (1994), two were developed. Remaining 12 items were measuring their perception about leadership style prevailing in their organization, four items were measuring for each three styles. Items about Autocratic style and democratic styles were adopted from questionnaire of Bhatti *et al* (2012), and items about Laissez-faire were developed. For ascertaining reliability of the questionnaire its internal consistency was checked prior to the main study, on the sample of 66 respondents using Cronbach Alpha and all items measuring a particular variable are having Cronbach's Alpha score > .60, Table 1 shows the reliability statistics of the questionnaire.

Table 1. Reliability Statistics for the Instrument

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Autocratic Leadership	.759	4
Democratic Leadership	.806	4
Laissez-Faire Leadership	.714	4
Job Satisfaction	.685	4

6. Results & discussion

The collected data were analyzed in terms of mean, standard deviation, chi square, and simple regression. The results of developed area and less-developed area are analyzed separately.

6.1 Leadership styles and Job satisfaction in developed cities

Job satisfaction of employees was analyzed and which leadership style is perceived to be applied in Banks was also determined, with the help of descriptive statistics.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of data from developed cities

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Job Satisfaction	66	3.1136	.63121
Autocratic Style	66	2.4583	.67166
Democratic Style	66	3.0076	.66357
Laissez-Fair Style	66	2.5038	.59241
Valid N (listwise)	66		

Most of the employees found satisfied with their job in the banks of developed city with mean score of 3.1136 (SD = 0.63121), though the satisfaction is not very high. Most of the employees perceived that there is democratic style applied in their organization by leaders because it has highest mean score of 3.0076 (SD = 0.66357). Table 2 exhibits the results.

Non parametric test Chi-Square (Goodness of fit test) was also performed. It was analyzed whether the null hypotheses against the alternate hypotheses is rejected or not, therefore Chi-Square test is performed and results are shown in Table 3.

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Table 3. Chi-Square test of hypotheses for developed cities

	Job Satisfaction	Autocratic Style	Democratic Style	Laissez-Fair Style
Chi-Square	79.152 ^a	22.364 ^b	16.727 ^a	40.061 ^a
Df	9	11	9	9
Asymp. Sig.	.000	.022	.053	.000

The null hypotheses have been rejected as all the variables have $p < .05$, except democratic leadership style which has $p > .05$, therefore the results about democratic style are not as significant as about other styles.

For knowing the influence of leadership styles on job satisfaction of bank employees of developed areas the simple regression was calculated, the results are shown below in Table 4, 5, and 6.

Table 4. Influence of Autocratic style in developed cities

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.103	.299		10.371	.000
	Autocratic Style	.004	.117	.005	.036	.971

a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

Autocratic leadership style was found to have least influence on job satisfaction of bank employees of developed area as it has insignificant beta coefficient .004. Which means it has no effect on job satisfaction of employees, Table 4 shows the results.

Table 5. Influence of democratic style in developed cities

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.780	.324		5.496	.000
	Democratic Style	.443	.105	.466	4.216	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

Democratic leadership style was found to have significant effects on job satisfaction of bank employees of developed area, as it has significant beta coefficient .443. It implies that democratic style of leadership can increase the job satisfaction of employees in banks of developed areas, exhibited by Table 5.

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Table 6. Influence of laissez-faire style in developed cities

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.642	.286		5.747	.000
	Laissez-faire Style	.588	.111	.552	5.292	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

Laissez-faire leadership style was found to have significant effect on job satisfaction of bank employees of developed area as it has significant beta coefficient .588. It has a higher effect than democratic style which implies the least involvement of leader makes the employees more satisfied in banks of developed cities, Table 6 indicates it.

6.2 Leadership styles and Job satisfaction in less-developed cities

Job satisfaction of employees and the leadership styles that are perceived to be applied in bank employees of less-developed areas were also analyzed in terms of mean and standard deviation.

Table 7. Descriptive statistics of data from less-developed cities

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Job Satisfaction	54	2.9120	.57083
Autocratic Style	54	2.6481	.67208
Democratic Style	54	2.7361	.58563
Laissez-Fair Style	54	2.5093	.54071
Valid N (listwise)	54		

As indicated by Table 7, employees of less-developed area are also found satisfied with their job with mean score of 2.9120 (SD = 0.57083) though the satisfaction is also not very high. Most of the employees perceived that there is democratic style applied in their organization by leaders because it has highest mean score of 2.7361 (SD = 0.58563).

It was analyzed whether the null hypotheses against the alternate hypotheses about employees of developed areas is rejected or not, therefore Chi-Square test is performed and results are exhibited in Table 8.

Table 8. Chi-Square test of hypotheses for less-developed cities

	Job Satisfaction	Autocratic Style	Democratic Style	Laissez-Fair Style
Chi-Square	38.481 ^a	31.704 ^b	31.778 ^c	20.000 ^d
Df	10	12	11	8
Asymp. Sig.	.000	.002	.001	.010

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The null hypotheses have been rejected as all the variables have $p < .05$, which means leadership styles in less-developed areas have significant effect on employees of bank. Simple regression was calculated for knowing the influence of leadership styles on job satisfaction of bank employees of less-developed areas. The tables 9, 10 and 11 exhibit the results below.

Table 9. Influence of Autocratic style in less-developed cities

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.456	.312		11.076	.000
	Autocratic Style	-.206	.114	-.242	-1.799	.078

a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

As shown by Table 9, Autocratic leadership style was found to have no effects on job satisfaction of bank employees of less-developed area as it has insignificant negative beta coefficient .206, which means under Autocratic leadership style employees are not satisfied with their job.

Table 10. Influence of democratic style in less-developed cities

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.254	.366		6.152	.000
	Democratic Style	.240	.131	.247	1.836	.072

a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

As exhibited by Table 10, Democratic leadership style was found to have insignificant positive effects on job satisfaction of bank employees of less-developed area as it has insignificant beta coefficient .240. Hence, democratic style affect insignificantly on job satisfaction of employees in less-developed areas.

Table 11. Influence of laissez-faire style in less-developed cities

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.964	.351		5.599	.000
	Laissez-Fair Style	.378	.137	.358	2.765	.008

a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

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As indicated by Table 11, Laissez-faire leadership style was found to have significant effect on job satisfaction of bank employees of less-developed area as it has significant beta coefficient .378. It has a higher and significant effect than democratic style, which means the passive role of leader is preferred by the employees over rigorous role of leader in banks of less-developed cities.

7. Conclusion & Recommendations

There was almost consensus among employees of developed and less-developed areas on job satisfaction and their perception about leadership style prevailing in their organization, whereas results are substantially different in terms of leadership styles' effect on job satisfaction of employees in both areas.

Autocratic style is least effective for creating job satisfaction among employees of developed areas and most effective is laissez-fair style. It can be assumed that employees of developed areas are more self-directed and need delegation rather than strictness and vigorous participation of their leader.

Autocratic Style affects insignificantly but negatively on employees' job satisfaction of less-developed areas. Laissez-fair was also found to be most effective in banks of less-developed areas. Whereas democratic style was also found insignificant in less-developed areas which was significant in developed areas. It implies that bank employees of less-developed areas are offended by autocratic style, and likely to be fugitive under democratic style and are happy in laissez-fair style.

The results are contrary to literature, as in almost all of the studies democratic leadership style was found to be most effective and laissez-fair was least effective. But in this study laissez-fair style positively effects on job satisfaction. Whereas in developed area, democratic style has moderate and significant effect on job satisfaction of bank employees but weak insignificant effect on job satisfaction of employees of less-developed areas. It is evident from the study, that autocratic leadership style decreases job satisfaction which is much consistent to literature.

The highest satisfaction towards laissez-faire is signaling that employees tend to be happy when they are free from the interference and strict eye of a boss. It can also be concluded that employees of banks are satisfied by some other factors rather than the leadership styles. More empirical studies can be conducted on job satisfaction as dependent variable and leadership styles along with other factors as independent variable, so that it can be determined that which factor increases job satisfaction more than the leadership style does.

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